

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M6.1 Initial DSS algorithm at an Operational Level

VERSION 1.1

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This milestone, namely M6.1, is part of Task 6.1 “Initial development and testing of an innovative Decision Support System” (Lead TUC, participants: UPV, UFZ, IST-ID, CERTE and BU), (Month 1 – Month 18). The aim of M6.1 is to describe the operation of the algorithm that is developed and will be applied to enable the decision support system (DSS). The DSS will aid groundwater managers in the sustainable management of groundwater resources taking into consideration multiple criteria: socio-economic and environmental. The algorithm is based on the multi-criteria optimization approach, thus meaning the formation of more than one objective functions. These objective functions refer to the respective criteria: optimum socio-economic management, optimum environmental management in terms of groundwater quantity and optimum environmental management in terms of groundwater quality.

Due to the fact that optimization processes are usually applied within iterative simulation runs of the study area model, they constitute a time-demanding procedure. Along with the non-linear nature of the problem, the model complexity and time needed are increased. Therefore, main focus has been given on efforts to overcome these difficulties, in order to provide the model with as much automation as possible. The DSS will be in line with a database from which

it can retrieve meteorological and hydrological data. The database is developed to function along with the DSS algorithm and its set up is also described in the current document.

1. The DSS tool

The aim of Work Package 6 is the development of a Decision Support System tool in order to aid decision-making for sustainable groundwater resources management. The decision-making tool will be based on a novel multi-criteria optimization methodology that will operate within a Fuzzy logic web-based Decision Support System. The multi-criteria optimization methodology will serve as the evaluation model for the assessment and recommendation of the optimum alternative solution(s). The fuzzy approach will be deployed in the development, training and testing of a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS). The Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) will be trained according to the data and the results achieved by the social, economic and environmental modelling and for the optimized results. In parallel, it will also be trained and tested under different scenarios, in order to retrieve a wide spectrum of fuzzy rules that will serve to finding the optimum alternative for all the considered criteria.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS)

As the criteria are of different nature, the quantitative values of the optimum results cannot be in the same scale. Therefore, fuzzy sets are used in order to provide a means of normalization and overlay of the criteria. The optimum results for each criterion and scenario are used in order to train a Fuzzy Inference System. Each criterion consists a different fuzzy rule, taking as input the problem variables. Through the FIS, the different fuzzy rules are overlaid and give as output the optimum result. Therefore, different alternatives can be

evaluated under different scenarios through the FIS. This way, the FIS will serve as a Decision Support System.

2. The Simulation – Optimization Procedure

The simulation – optimization procedure refers to the separate simulation and optimization of each criterion that is taken into consideration. For each criterion, a different analysis is conducted according to its nature. This way, the optimum value for the examined scenario is obtained for each criterion. The objective functions (criteria) and constraints were selected so as to be applicable in all five case study areas of InTheMED project by addressing to the environmental issues that these areas have in common; overexploitation (except Castro Verde) and groundwater pollution (except Requena – Utiel), along with the socio-economic criteria.

Figure 2. Graphic representation of simulation - optimization procedure and FIS training

In the following sections, the simulation model and the optimization procedure for the selected criteria are described.

2.1. Socio-economic criteria

A socioeconomic approach was established for the area considering socioeconomic data analysis and Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios using a statistical model and the WEAP model to identify the dynamics of social factors (population, economy) and agriculture (production, efficiency) in terms of water availability and use. Basic socioeconomic indicators (population, GDP, agriculture production) in the region are explored and the future trends are determined considering three different climate change RCP scenarios and relative Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios (IIASA - International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis) e.g. Fig 3. The development of more specific socioeconomic indicators such as agricultural intensity, crops, and land use is also investigated. The indicators' projected development is examined combining climate change RCP scenarios with SSP and the associated projected water availability to provide the expected climate change effect in the socioeconomic context. Another significant indicator that was investigated under green socioeconomic development was the capacity of the reservoir located in the area of study. The task considered the climatic scenarios effect in the reservoir's capacity. The WEAP model and a statistical model, is used to provide the projections on socioeconomic factors and water availability (basin, reservoir) Fig 4 and 5.

Figure 3. GDP projection under Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios

Figure 4. Projected Irrigation demand and water allocation from groundwater (green) and Faneromeni reservoir (red) using climate change scenarios, population variation, agricultural water demand and projected water availability through WEAP model

Figure 5. Schematic approach of the main demand sites and water sources, and their interconnections in Messara basin using WEAP model

2.1.1 Cost – Benefit Analysis (CBA)

Bayesian decision analysis is usually employed to make decisions in the presence of uncertainty. A common cost-benefit analysis approach coupled with Bayesian decision analysis are applied to aid the decision making of implementing mitigation measures for groundwater resources management. To this end, the full cost-benefit methodology has been established and the optimal options for managed use of groundwater. The mapping of those options is a dynamical process and will be adjusted over the course of the project, where key stakeholders can be added at a different stage to enrich the multi-stakeholder partnership process. The provided information will give insights into assessing the sustainability of the current and future groundwater management strategies. This analysis will identify the impact of the adequate mitigation option considering sustainable water resources availability, management and potential pollution risks.

The decision-making process involves two stages: state estimation and decision making. For state estimation, firstly, all the state parameters θ_i are defined. However, in the Bayesian approach, a state parameter is an unknown quantity and is considered a random variable that must be determined. The procedure of estimating each θ_i involves previous knowledge on the examined issue and the use of the subjective prior distribution $\pi(\theta_i)$ that expresses the prior information for each state parameter. Next, the Bayesian risk function is obtained to estimate the optimal decision or the decision with the minimum expected risk. The latter also applies in terms of a cost-benefit analysis procedure and denotes the preferable action. The Bayesian decision-making process follows these four steps, while a detailed approach is presented in the flowchart of Fig. 6:

1. Set up the decision-making problem by introducing the possible actions set A and the parametric space θ .
2. Establish the expected loss function for each decision $A(i)$, and provide the state of the goal function. If at this step, the parameters θ_i are considered known, then the decision process is called a cost-benefit analysis, and Step 4 is directly applied. If not, then both Steps 3 and 4 apply.

3. Develop the subjective prior distributions for each θ_i quantifying the previous information.
4. Combine Steps 1, 2, and 3 via the risk function. The decision with the minimum expected risk is the optimal decision.

Figure 6. Flowchart of Bayesian Risk and cost-benefit risk analysis

2.2. Environmental criteria

2.2.1. Groundwater quantity

The simulation – optimization procedure consists of 2 components/sub-routines.

1. The construction of a response matrix based on iterative simulation runs of the groundwater model.
2. The optimization of the pumping rates by using the response matrix.

The response matrix is created by sequentially disturbing the initial pumping rates of the m pumping wells, then running the simulation model and obtaining the hydraulic heads in n observation wells. The response matrix A is the $n \times m$ matrix, with its elements consisting of the values of hydraulic head's response to the disturbance of the pumping rate: $\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q}$.

Then, the optimization problem is set as:

$$\max Q$$

$$s. t. : H \geq H_{ref}$$

Where: $H = H_o + \partial H$ and $\partial H = A * \partial Q$

Therefore, the constraint:

$$H_o + \partial H \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$H_o + A * \partial Q \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$H_o + A * (Q - Q_o) \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$A * Q \geq H_{ref} - H_o + A * Q_o$$

The problem is transformed to be in line with the requirements of Matlab optimization tool as:

$$\min(-Q)$$

$$s. t. : -A * Q \leq H_o - H_{ref} - A * Q_o$$

– A , the constraint coefficients matrix and

$b = H_o - H_{ref} - A * Q_o$, the vector of constraints of the linear problem.

Although the problem is not linear, it is solved by using the Simplex method in the frame of the piece-wise linear technique. Thus, after the first simulation – optimization cycle, the results for the optimum pumping rates are used in order to run again the simulation procedure, create the response matrix and apply the optimization procedure. The cycle is repeated until the results of two consecutive cycles converge to the same value.

The preliminary results of the previously described simulation – optimization procedure show that a reduction of up to 50.2% (from $6.231 \cdot 10^3 \text{ m}^3$ to $3.103 \cdot 10^3 \text{ m}^3$) should be applied on the pumping rates during the summer period in order to achieve a m raise of the groundwater level and push back the salinization front. In the following figure 5, the tendency of the pumping rates to converge towards similar values along the simulation – optimization runs are shown as for the first 6 realizations of the procedure.

Figure 7. Optimal pumping rates for the dry season for the different model runs

In order to overcome the difficulties of the time-demanding runs of the groundwater simulation model, the response matrices can be constructed by using the results of the hydraulic heads and pumping rate values retrieved from a corresponding surrogate model. The ANN groundwater model that is being developed in WP3 of the project will be taken into consideration for integration into the simulation – optimization procedure. This way, the procedure can be fully automated, with no dependencies on the manual handling of a mainstream computational groundwater model.

3 Environmental Data Management System

An environmental data management system has been created in order to gather and mine the environmental data. The design of the database includes the storage of the collected data in a coherent environmental database management system (DBMS) for further use within the project. A critical issue that was taken into is the existence of queries for automatic updating, importing data, exporting data, selecting specific subsets and grouping records. The database was connected with an open-source business intelligence tool, which helps users question the database and visualize answers in useful optical formats that can be shared.

3.1. Type of Database

The two most common types of databases are the relational and Not only SQL databases (NoSQL). The relational model, introduced by Edgar F. Codd in the early 1970's, defines a methodology for organizing structured data into relations (tables with columns and rows) and for defining the relationships between those tables. Each table contains a primary key and must be indexed. A primary key is a field which is guaranteed to have a unique entry for each record in a table. Indexes provide a quick navigation through the database, in order to retrieve specific data subsets. The entries in the attribute chosen as index should be unique or rare, within that field. Usually, the primary key will be chosen as an index, although this is not a requirement. Relational databases can be normalised to improve performance of queries, reduce data duplication and make the database more elegant.

At the heart of the relational model is the Structured Query Language (SQL), a standards-based programming language used to define database schema and the relationships between tables. The language is also used to store, manipulate, and retrieve data from those tables. SQL has been adopted by both the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and is well known and widely supported by developers around the globe.

Relational databases offer many important features that make them aptly suited to enterprise workloads, which is why organizations have been turning to them for so long. They're

optimized for handling highly structured data, and their inherent characteristics—such as normalization, atomicity, and consistency—ensure the integrity of that data throughout its lifespan. These features also contribute to better storage utilization, while providing flexible query support through standards-based SQL. However, relational databases are not appropriate for semi-structured or unstructured data, especially at scale. A relational database also requires a rigid schema that must be carefully planned and does not easily accommodate changing requirements, leaving little room for the dynamic nature of many of today’s applications and development methodologies.

Due to the existence of highly structured data in the current project, the database schema is predefined, resulting in a rigid structure that helps to optimize storage and ensure data integrity. Furthermore, there is a crucial need for performing complex queries against the structured data. Finally, a high degree of data integrity, adhering to the principles of atomicity, consistency, isolation, and durability is also necessary, along with a mature database technology, that is supported by large developer communities. Thus, a relational database best suits the needs of the current project.

3.2. Relational Database Management System

MySQL is a popular, high performance, open-source, relational DBMS (Database Management System), paired with ongoing development and support from Oracle. MySQL can be used in conjunction with MySQL Workbench, a unified visual tool which provides data modeling, SQL development and comprehensive administration tools for server configuration, user administration, backup, and much more. It is platform agnostic and makes interactions with relational databases much easier. Often associated with internet applications or web services, MySQL was designed to be extensively compatible with other technologies and architectures. The RDBMS runs on all major computing platforms, including Unix-based operating systems, such as the myriad Linux distributions or Mac OS and Windows. MySQL’s client-server architecture means it can support a variety of backends, as well as different programming interfaces. Third-party migration tools further allow MySQL to move data to and from a vast set of general storage systems, whether these are designed to be on-premises or cloud-based.

MySQL can be deployed in virtualized environments, distributed or centralized, and even exists as portable standalone libraries for learning purposes, testing, or small applications. MySQL's wide compatibility with all these other systems and software makes it a particularly practical choice of RDBMS in most situations. Any individual or enterprise may freely use, modify, publish, and expand on Oracle's open-source MySQL code base. The software is released under the GNU General Public License (GPL). The public and community-based nature of open-source releases enriches MySQL's documentation and online support culture, while also ensuring that sustained or newly-developed capabilities never stray too far from current user needs.

Due to the features described above, MySQL is perfectly suited for the environmental data within this project, so it will be used for all interactions throughout it.

3.3. Design Features

Normalization is a database design technique that reduces data redundancy and eliminates undesirable characteristics like insertion, update and deletion anomalies. Normalization rules divide larger tables into smaller and link them using relationships. Thus, Normal Forms are used to eliminate or reduce redundancy in database tables. There are different levels of normalisation, such as:

- **1st Normal Form (1NF)**

If a relation contains composite or multi-valued attribute, it violates first Normal Form or a relation is in first Normal Form if it does not contain any composite or multi-valued attribute. Thus, repeated sets of related data are removed and put into an individual table, where each set of related data has its own separate table and is identified with a primary key.

- **2nd Normal Form (2NF)**

To be in second Normal Form, a relation must be in first normal form and relation must not contain any partial dependency. A relation is in 2NF if it has no partial dependency, i.e., no non-prime attribute (attributes which are not part of any candidate key) is dependent on any proper subset of any candidate key of the table.

- **3rd Normal Form (3NF)**

A table is considered in third Normal Form if the table/entity is already in the second Normal Form and the columns of the table/entity are non-transitively dependent on the primary key.

- **Boyce-Codd Normal Form (BCNF)**

A relation is in Boyce-Codd Normal Form (BCNF) if every determinant is a candidate key. The difference between 3NF and BCNF is that for a functional dependency $A \rightarrow B$, 3NF allows this dependency in a relation if B is a primary-key attribute and A is not a candidate key, whereas BCNF insists that for this dependency to remain in a relation, A must be a candidate key.

In the context of the current project, every table was designed by means of describing one characteristic (i.e. weather station, temperature measurement, rain measurement) and the associated data which is necessary for describing that characteristic. 3NF normalization was used in order to eliminate or reduce redundancy in database tables and to improve the performance of queries. Thus, every table present on the database satisfies the criteria of 2NF, non-primary key columns shouldn't depend on other non-primary key columns and there is absence of transitive functional dependencies.

3.4. Metabase: a brief overview

Metabase is a rapidly growing open source business intelligence tool, crafted in such a way that all kinds of charts, plots and graphs with different designs can be positioned simultaneously for data visualization. Moreover, Metabase's intuitive interface lets you ask questions on your data and displays answers in famous downloadable formats. Questions can be saved, making it easy to come back to them and they can also be grouped into dashboards in order to be shared with the rest of your team. Metabase uses the MariaDB connector to connect easily to MariaDB and MySQL servers. It sets up really quickly, connecting to your database and bringing its data to life in beautiful visualizations, opening data up for everyone, not just analysts and developers

Metabase home page allows some automatic explorations of the tables that a user can look at and save as a dashboard, an area where things that the teammates create will show up, along with a link to explore all the created dashboards and saved questions. Once some dashboards have been created, any of them that are pinned in the main “Our analytics” collection will show up on the homepage for all of the teammates.

3.4.1. Browsing data

If a connection is finally established between Metabase and a database, the current database is listed at the bottom of the homepage along with the sample dataset that Metabase comes with. Users can easily click on a database to see its contents and can easily click on a table to see its rows. Moreover, by clicking on the bolt icon to x-ray a table, the user can see an automatic exploration of it. Metabase can present the data in a variety of ways, just by changing the visualization mode from the “Visualization” sidebar.

The screenshot shows the Metabase interface with a table visualization of temperature measurement data. The table has the following columns: IdTemp, TempDate, TempM, TempH, TempHTime, TempL, TempLTime, and StationIdStation. The data is displayed for 11 rows, showing temperature measurements from November 1, 2009, to November 11, 2009. The interface includes a search bar, a navigation menu, and various action buttons like 'Save', 'Filter', and 'Summarize'.

IdTemp	TempDate	TempM	TempH	TempHTime	TempL	TempLTime	StationIdStation
1	November 1, 2009	15.4	17	12:50 AM	13.5	6:50 PM	1
2	November 2, 2009	14.3	15.6	1:50 PM	12.4	2:50 AM	1
3	November 3, 2009	17.1	21.6	11:20 PM	11.5	3:00 AM	1
4	November 4, 2009	18.8	21.1	1:10 PM	15.3	9:00 AM	1
5	November 5, 2009	18.5	22.5	3:30 PM	13.9	5:40 AM	1
6	November 6, 2009	20.6	22.1	12:40 PM	16.7	12:40 AM	1
7	November 7, 2009	20.9	22.2	1:40 PM	20.1	7:00 AM	1
8	November 8, 2009	19.7	21.7	7:00 AM	16.8	10:10 AM	1
9	November 9, 2009	18.6	22.2	1:00 PM	14.6	7:00 AM	1
10	November 10, 2009	20.8	23.2	10:50 AM	15.7	12:30 AM	1
11	November 11, 2009	20.2	22.2	12:40 AM	17.7	7:30 AM	1

Figure 8. Sample visualization of temperature data as a table

Figure 9. Sample visualization of temperature data as a scatter-plot

3.4.2. Asking Questions

Metabase’s two core concepts are questions and their corresponding answers. Everything else is based around questions and answers. A user can ask a question in Metabase by clicking the “Ask a Question” button at the top of the screen. There are three ways to ask a specific question in Metabase:

- The simple question mode, which lets the user filter, summarize and visualize data.
- The custom question mode, which gives the user a powerful notebook-style editor to create more complex questions that require joins, multiple stages of filtering and aggregating, or custom columns.
- The SQL/native query editor.

The answers can be downloaded as an .xlsx, .csv, or .json file. The maximum download size is 1 million rows.

3.4.2.1. Simple Questions

After the user selects the Simple Question option, he will need to pick some data that has a question about. The Simple Question could be on a user's table or something like events, orders or downloads. Moreover, there are options for filtering data and/or summarizing them. By clicking the "Filter" option, a list of all of the columns in the browsed table, as well as columns from tables that are related to the current table, appears. Depending on the column picked, there are slightly different options for the filter. Generally, there are three types of columns, each with their own set of filtering options:

- Numeric columns let the user add filters to only include table rows where the values of the attribute are between two specific values, greater or less than a specific value or exactly equal to a specific value.
- With text or category columns, users can specify that only want to include data where this column is or isn't a specific option or can exclude rows that don't have a value for this column.
- Date columns give a calendar or input box so that specific time ranges or all days before or after a certain date can be selected.

Metabase administrators own the option to create special named filters for the tables and if they do so, the filters appear at the top of the filter dropdown in purple text with a star next to them. These are called "segments" and they are shortcuts to a combination of filters that are commonly used by the members of the team sharing the database.

The "Summarize" option has two main parts. The metric desired and the type of data group. By default, the "count of rows" metric will be selected, since it's super common, but it can easily be changed. The user can also select more than one metric to view. The available metrics are listed below:

- Count of rows: the total of number of rows in the table, after any filters have been applied.
- Sum of: the sum of all the values in a specific column.

- Average of: the average of all the values in a single column.
- Number of distinct values of: the number of unique values in all the cells of a single column.
- Cumulative sum of: a running total for a specific column. In order for this metric to be useful the user needs to group it by a date column to see it across time.
- Cumulative count of rows: a running total of the number of rows in the table over time. Just like “Cumulative sum of”, the user needs to group this by a date column in order for it to be useful.
- Standard deviation of: a number which expresses how much the values of a column vary, plus or minus, from the average value of that column.
- Minimum of: the minimum value present in the selected field.
- Maximum of: the maximum value present in the selected field.

Figure 10. Sample of summarizing data in a simple question

3.4.2.2. Custom Questions with Notebook Editor

If the user has a question that's a bit more involved than a simple question, he can create a custom question using the notebook editor, by clicking the "Ask a Question" button in the top navigation bar and selecting "Custom Question".

The notebook is made up of a sequence of individual steps. Under each step, there are buttons to add more steps after the current one. To the right of each step is a preview button that shows the first 10 rows of the results of the question up to that step.

This first step is required and is where the user picks the data that wants to base the question on. In most cases, users pick one of the tables in the database created, but they can also choose a previously saved question's result as the starting point for the new question. What this means in practice is that the user can do things like use complex SQL queries to create new tables that can be used as starting data in a question just like any other table in your database.

The users can have most saved questions as source data, provided they have permission to view that question. They can even use questions that were saved as a chart rather than a table. Although, there are some kinds of saved questions that can't be used as source data:

- Druid questions,
- Google Analytics questions,
- Mongo questions,
- questions that use "Cumulative Sum" or "Cumulative Count" aggregations,
- questions that have columns that are named the same or similar thing, like "Count" and "Count 2".

During the next step of custom question design, the user has the option to select one or more columns to filter on. Adding a summarize step lets the user choose how to aggregate the data from the previous step. He can pick one or more metrics and optionally group those metrics by one or more columns. When picking the metrics, the user can choose from basic functions

like sum, average and count, can pick a common metric that an admin has defined or can create a custom expression by writing a formula.

Furthermore, the user can join data to combine current table with others or even with a saved question. Currently joins are not available, if the starting data is from a Google Analytics or MongoDB database. After clicking on the 'Join Data' button to add a join step, the user needs to pick the data that he wants to join. It's important, that he can only pick tables and saved questions that are from the same database as your starting data. Next, the user needs to pick the columns he wants to join on. This means that he must pick a column from the first table and a column from the second table and the join will stitch rows together where the value from the first column is equal to the value in the second column. A very common example is to join on an ID column in each table, so if happened to pick a table to join on where there is a foreign key relationship between the tables, Metabase will automatically pick those corresponding ID columns. At the end of join step, there's a 'Columns' button that the user can click to choose which columns he wants to include from the joined data. By default, Metabase will do a left outer join, but there is a Venn diagram icon to select a different type of join. Metabase supports multiple stages of joins and joins on multiple conditions. Not all databases support all types of joins, so Metabase will only display the options supported by the database you're using.

Here are the basic types of joins:

- Left outer join: select all records from Table A, along with records from Table B that meet the join condition, if any.
- Right outer join: select all records from Table B, along with records from Table A that meet the join condition, if any.
- Inner join: only select the records from Table A and B where the join condition is met.
- Full outer join: select all records from both tables, whether or not the join condition is met.

Figure 11. Sample of implementing a custom question (joining and filtering), through Notebook Editor

3.4.2.3 Advanced Questions in Native Query Editor

If a user has the permissions to use the Native Query Editor, he can directly write SQL or his database's native querying language. If any user writes a SQL query that includes variables, the question might have filter widgets at the top of the screen. Filter widgets let the user modify the SQL query before its run, changing the final results. Any team member can use SQL snippets to save, reuse and share SQL code across multiple questions that are composed using the SQL editor.

Figure 12. Sample of implementing an advanced question in Native Query Editor

3.4.3. Dashboards, Collections, Pulses

Dashboards group questions and present them on a single page. Dashboards are shareable reports that feature a set of related questions. Subscriptions to dashboards can be set via email or Slack to receive the exported results of the dashboard's questions. A dashboard comprises a set of cards arranged on a grid. These cards can be questions, such as tables, charts, maps or text boxes. Users can add filter widgets to dashboards that filter data identically across multiple questions and customize what happens when their teammates click on a chart or a table. In Metabase parlance, every chart on a dashboard is called a "question." Clicking on the title of a question on a dashboard will take the user to a detail view of that question. When you're looking at the detail view of a question, you can use all the same actions mentioned above. You can also click on the headings of tables to see more options, like summing the values of a column, or filtering based on that column. If the Metabase administrator has enabled public sharing on a dashboard, the user can go to that dashboard and click on the sharing icon to find its public links. Public links can be viewed by anyone, even if they don't have access to Metabase. The public embedding code can be used to embed the dashboard in a simple web page or a blog post.

Collections in Metabase are a lot like folders. They're where all team's dashboards and charts are kept. In order to explore a collection, a user must just click on one in the "Our analytics" section of the home page or click on "Browse all items".

The Pulses feature in Metabase gives users the ability to automatically send regular updates to their teammates to help everyone keep track of changes to the metrics that matter them most. Because of the space constraints of email and Slack, Metabase will automatically make some adjustments to the appearance of the saved question so that it looks great in the Pulse. For example, in order to save space, pie charts will automatically be transformed into bar charts. Users can also optionally include the results of a saved question in an emailed pulse as a .csv or .xls file attachment. Users can also set a different delivery schedule for email versus Slack. To deliver by email, the users have to type in the Metabase user names, or email addresses they want to send the pulse to, separated by commas. Then, they have to choose to either send it daily, weekly, or monthly and the time at which they want it to be sent. To send via

Slack, the users need to choose which channel they want to post the pulse in, whether they want it to post hourly or daily and at what time. Again, the schedule for Slack can be different from the schedule for email.

The search bar is a quick way to find dashboards, questions, collections and pulses. The user can select from the typeahead's dropdown results or hit enter to view a search results page.

Figure 13. Sample dashboard